

Assessment of Risk Factors for COVID-19 among Undergraduate Medical Students on Field Duty for Covid Management at Ahmedabad City, A Retrospective Case-Control Study

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Abstract:

Background: For a long, medical students have not been posted for compulsory management of public health emergencies of international concern. Hence globally, there is a paucity of data on the risk of infection among medical students who are posted for field duty at primary health centres. This study evaluates risk factors of COVID-19 among medical students posted for management of covid-19 pandemic at the primary healthcare level.

Methods: This retrospective case-control study was conducted on 221 medical students who were posted at a primary healthcare facility for COVID-19 management during March-May 2021. Students positive for SARS-COV-2 were the cases (n=71) and those negative for SARS-COV-2 were the control (n= 150). Univariate analysis was followed by multivariate analysis for key epidemiological variables.

Results: On univariate analysis, type of duty, place of duty, history of migration, history of high-risk contacts, academic standard, place of residence during duty, use of air conditioning, etc. were found to be significantly associated with Covid positivity. On multivariate analysis, type of duty ($p < 0.00001$) and place of residence during duty ($p < 0.0033$) were significantly associated with Covid-19 infection among students. Two-dose immunization against COVID-19 (OR = 0.63) and satisfaction regarding preplacement training (OR = 0.43 – 0.80) emerged as protective factors.

Conclusion: Duty at mass COVID testing centers and staying in a hostel during duty period predisposes medical students to COVID-19 infection while being fully immunized and a high level of satisfaction regarding pre-placement training protects them from infection.

Keywords: COVID-19, Duty, Healthcare, Medical Students.

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Introduction

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is an infectious disease caused by Severe Acute Respiratory Corona Virus-2 (SARS-CoV-2) [1]. The disease was first identified in December 2019 in Wuhan city of China and has since spread to many countries including India [2]. The World Health Organization (WHO) declared it a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEI) and on 11 April 2020, it was declared as a pandemic [3]. Healthcare workers are at higher risk of contracting this highly contagious virus. Globally, many casualties reported among healthcare workers during this pandemic [4][5]. As the pandemic continued, the healthcare system of

many countries either struggled to sustain or collapsed, due to a shortage of healthcare personnel, medical facilities, and/or equipment. Many countries including India have posted undergraduate medical students as support staff to handle this situation [6][7]. In Ahmedabad, the largest city of Gujarat province in India, these students were posted at urban primary health care facility during 2nd wave of the pandemic in the year 2021 [8] [9] [10] [11].

Methodology

A retrospective case-control study was conducted at B. J. Medical College, Ahmedabad after

obtaining approval from the institutional ethical committee (Ref. No. EC/Approval/89/2021). B.J. Medical College is one of the largest medical colleges in India with an annual intake capacity of 250 students. Participants included 501 undergraduate medical students who were on duty for COVID-19 management at Ahmedabad city during 2nd wave of disease from March to May 2021.

The students were trained and posted at two places: 1) the COVID-19 mass testing team (dome duty) to perform on-the-spot RAT test, report and counsel the visitors and 2) the home care team (Sanjeevani

duty) to take care of mild/moderate covid-19 positive cases who were home isolated. They had to work under the joint supervision of the community medicine department and medical officer at urban health centers.

The case was defined as a medical student who tested positive for COVID-19 either by RT-PCR or Rapid Antigen Test (RAT) report during duty period. Gender-stratified controls were selected from medical students who performed duty during the same period but never tested positive for COVID-19. Those who didn't give consent for the study were excluded (Flow chart 1).

Flow chart 1: Data collection

A pretested predesigned proforma was electronically sent to participants after explaining the purpose of the study and was used to collect data regarding academic year, gender, age, type of duty, COVID-19 infection, migration before duty, vaccination status, high-risk contact, COVID-19 training, place of stay, etc. The data thus collected was entered in Microsoft Excel-19 and analyzed using Epi-info software. Continuous data were

summarized as frequency/percentage. The mean, standard deviation, and range were calculated. Univariate analysis was followed by multivariate analysis for key epidemiological variables.

The odds ratio, 95% confidence interval, and chi-square were calculated. The values of $p < 0.05$ were considered significant.

Results

Table 1: Basic profile of undergraduate medical students on duty for COVID-19 management.

		Case (N=71)	Control (N=150)
Age in years (mean \pm 2SD)		20.21 \pm 0.82	20.26 \pm 0.88
Gender	Boys	58 (81%)	119 (79.3%)
	Girls	13 (16.9%)	31 (20.7%)

* $p < 0.05$ is significant

Table 1 shows 71 cases and 150 controls with a ratio of 1:2. The mean age of cases was 20.21 \pm 0.82 years and that of controls was 20.26 \pm 0.88 years. Out of 217 boys, 58 (81%) were cases and 119 (79.3%) were controls, and out of 44 girls, 13 (16.9%) were cases and 31 (20.7%) were controls.

Table 2: Risk factors for COVID-19 among undergraduate medical students on duty for COVID-19 management

Variables		Case (N=71)	Control (N=150)	OR (95% CI)
Academic year	2 nd year	56 (78.9%)	111 (74%)	1.31
	3 rd year	15 (21.1%)	39 (26%)	(0.67-2.58)
High-risk contact **	Yes	36 (50.7%)	49 (32.7%)	2.12
	No	35 (49.3%)	101(67.3%)	(1.19- 3.77)
History of Migration*	Yes	32 (47.9%)	38 (27.3%)	2.44
	No	39 (52.1%)	112 (72.7%)	(1.35- 4.39)
Place of stay*	Hostel	57 (80.3%)	72 (48%)	4.41
	Home	14 (19.7%)	78 (52%)	(2.26- 8.54)
Air conditioning in hostel	Yes	16 (22.5%)	20 (13.3%)	1.01
	No	55 (77.5%)	130 (86.7%)	(0.40- 2.20)
Air conditioning in the home	Yes	12 (16.9%)	69 (46%)	0.78
	No	59 (83.1%)	81 (54%)	(0.15- 4.00)
Type of duty*	Mass testing dome duty	13 (18.3%)	2 (1.3%)	16.59
	Sanjeevani ghar sewa	58 (81.7%)	148 (98.7%)	(3.62- 75.82)
PPE training	Satisfied	63 (88.7%)	142 (94.7%)	0.44
	Not satisfied	8 (11.3%)	8 (5.3%)	(0.16- 1.20)
Hand washing/sanitization training	Satisfied	62 (87.3%)	141 (94%)	0.43
	Not satisfied	9 (12.7%)	9 (6%)	(0.17- 1.16)
Swab collection training	Satisfied	58 (81.7%)	126 (84%)	0.80
	Not satisfied	13 (18.3%)	24 (16%)	(0.40- 1.80)
Vaccination Status	Complete (2 dose)	39 (54.9%)	99 (66%)	0.63
	Partial (1 dose)/ not vaccinated	32 (45.1%)	51 (49%)	(0.35-1.12)

*: $p < 0.05$ is significant. #: contact with COVID-19 patient within 1meter or with their body fluid (without self-protective measures) [12]

Table 2 shows that the risk of infection for COVID-19 was higher among those medical students who did have high-risk contacts (OR: 2.12) during duty, history of migration before

joining duty (OR: 2.44), staying at the hostel during duty period (OR:4.41) and being posted at covid-19 mass testing duty (OR:16.59). These findings were statistically significant. Being a 2nd

year medical student is also a possible risk factor (OR: 1.31). All three training components: hand washing (OR: 0.43), Personal Protective Equipment (OR: 0.44), and swab collection (OR: 0.80) have turned out to be possible protective

factors. Complete vaccination (2 dose-covishield) also seems to offer possible protection (OR: 0.63). However, these results are statistically not significant.

Table 3: Risk factors for COVID-19 among undergraduate medical students on duty for COVID-19 management (multiple logistic regression)

Variables	t ratio	p-value	Significant contribution
Mass testing duty	4.069	<0.00001	Yes
History of migration	0.309	0.7576	No
Hostel as a place of stay	2.975	0.0033	Yes
High-risk contact	1.459	0.1459	No

Table 3 shows that mass testing duty ($p < 0.00001$) and hostel as a place of stay while on duty ($p < 0.0033$) were significant contributors to case positivity among medical students on duty.

Discussion

This study was conducted to assess risk factors for COVID-19 among undergraduate medical students who were posted at primary healthcare facilities for COVID-19 management. Practically speaking, no such research has been conducted in the past. Hence we discussed risk factors for COVID-19 among health workers in hospital settings with relevant articles.

Mass testing duty/dome duty is a significant risk factor (OR: 16.59, p-value: <0.0001) for COVID-19 for students in this study. Mass testing is a screening place, sometimes overcrowded with long queues of suspected or probable cases who generally are not aware of COVID-19 protocol i.e. safe distancing, mask-wearing, and safe hand hygiene. And when students attend them with a lack of caution, it puts them at higher risk. The finding is comparable with studies conducted by Yan Qian et al in Wuhan, China among nurses of Tongji Hospital [13].

In our study, we found hostel as a place of stay while on duty is a significant risk factor for COVID-19 infection (OR- 4.41, p-value <0.0001). This outcome is supported by a study by Xiaoquan Lai et al [14] and Silvio A. Namendys-Silva et al [15]. Vivek Kak et al [16]. Also states the significance of closed environments like ships, barracks, and college dormitories in the spread of respiratory infection.

Our study found the history of migration, 14 days before joining duty as a risk factor for covid-19 (OR:2.44, p-value:0.0042). This may be due to their contact with asymptomatic/symptomatic cases during travel. Michael W. Levin et al [17] also prove the contribution of travel to the spread of infection.

High-risk contact within a 1-meter distance without a mask is found significantly risky (OR-2.21, p-

value- 0.015) in this study. This outcome is in agreement with a study conducted by Roger Chouet et al [18], and Marjolein F. Q. et al [19]. And Sugandhi Sharma et al [20] in hospital settings.

We found more cases from 2nd-year MBBS students than that from 3rd-year students. We have taken several controls based on cases but otherwise strength of both batches is equal. This points towards less academic maturity of 2nd year students. Merida Rodriguez-Lopez et al [21] also reported that healthcare workers with higher graduation have lesser chances of infection.

Our study shows that being vaccinated for COVID-19 (covishield vaccine) is a possible protective factor (OR: 0.63). This finding is similar to a study done at JIMPER Pondicherry by Stuti Pramod et al which also proved this vaccine to be protective[22].

Training is an important component of the preparation of healthcare workers for Covid challenges. A study in Wuhan conducted by Xin Tong et al concluded that zero occupational infection is an achievable goal with appropriate training, strict compliance, and psychological support for the frontline HCWs [23].

In our study, the response of participants toward training was positive, and more than 80% of participants were satisfied with the training before placement. This was in contrast to the finding by Barbara Źóltowska et al [24]. Who reported only a 45.8% level of satisfaction.

Satisfaction in training is found to be a protective factor in our study with an odds ratio of 0.43 – 0.80 for various components like safe distancing, hand hygiene, and mask-wearing. Nishanth Dev et al, [25] reported a lack of training as a significant risk factor for covid-19 infectivity.

Our study put in new knowledge regarding care to be taken while posting undergraduate medical students for compulsory duty at the primary healthcare level. The findings will be useful for academicians/controllers and public health managers engaged in crisis management with a shortage of staff. This study highlights the

importance of adhering to COVID-19 prevention protocol and pre-placement training to minimize the risk of COVID-19. As with any other retrospective study, there may be recall bias while collecting data. The single-center nature of the study is also a limiting factor.

Conclusion

Placement at mass testing duty, joining within 14 days of migration, staying in a hostel, high-risk contacts predisposed undergraduate medical students for COVID-19 infection while being fully immunized and high level of satisfaction regarding pre-placement training protected them from getting infection. These factors should be taken into consideration while posting them for crisis management in the future.

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